

Assessing the role of radio as a tool for public enlightenment towards achieving clean environment in Ilorin metropolis

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World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2025, 27(01), 2515-2531

Publication history: Received on 19 June 2025; revised on 27 July 2025; accepted on 30 July 2025

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2025.27.1.2793>

Abstract

The study assessed the role of radio as a tool for public enlightenment towards achieving a clean environment in the Ilorin metropolis. The study was anchored on Development Media Theory. A survey research method was adopted while a questionnaire was administered to elicit responses from respondents. Quota sampling techniques and accidental sampling techniques were selected Respondents. Equally, the data were analyzed in descriptive statistics (frequency and percentage) with the aid of tables. Finding revealed that the majority of respondents (64%) listen to environmental sanitation programmes on radio often. Also, the majority of respondents (65%) agree that sanitation programmes on radio sensitize them about environmental cleaning. Many of respondents (54%) agree that sanitation campaigns on radio were effective. However, the majority of respondents (54%) want radio stations to double their effort towards enlightening people about environmental sanitation. It was recommended that a special desk to be called environmental and climate desk should be created and equipped with scientific and investigative journalists to maintain the desk for effective and efficient dissemination of information on sanitation, weather, climate and other environmental matters.

Keywords: Environmental Communication; Development Media Theory; Communication for Development (C4D); Media and Health Behavior

1. Introduction

Environmental sanitation is a health matter that seeks to properly clean the environment in order to avoid environmental pollution, air-borne diseases, water borne diseases and other environmental problems, more importantly, maintaining personal hygiene. According to a report from the Nigeria Centre for Disease Control (NCDC), Cholera has claimed more lives in Nigeria than the dreaded coronavirus pandemic, especially in 2021. The centre's director general, Ifedayo Adetifa, said the country has recorded "a little more than 3,600" deaths from cholera in the last 11 months while the total fatalities recorded from coronavirus since 2022 when the index case was recorded still stands at 2,977 (Mariam, 2021).

NCDC is currently dealing with some fresh outbreaks, there is a connection between this and the rainy season, for example. So when you've got the rains and areas with open defecation, and normal water sources are then flooded by rainwater and mixed and then you have a problem. NCDC also urged state authorities to invest in water and sanitation across the federation. NCDC also pointed out that as of November 2121, Nigeria has recorded a total of 3,566 deaths and 103,589 suspected cholera cases across 32 states of the federation and the FCT – a 3.4 per cent Case Fatality Ratio. According to the centre, four states- Bauchi (19,470 cases), Jigawa (13,293 cases) Kano (12,116 cases), and Zamfara (11,918 cases) account for 55 per cent of all cumulative cases (Mariam, 2021).

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According to Anijah (2013), throughout the world, the problem of polluted environment has become a very disturbing phenomenon. Environmental problems plaguing the world are enormous. But perhaps the most serious and worrisome in Nigeria is the physical environment in terms of the low level of sanitation and gross environmental indiscipline in our cities and communities.

Anijah (2013) added that apart from the health significance of heaps of refuse as a health hazard, they also make our environment ugly. The problem of solid waste disposal in Nigeria has become a national malaise. Filth is an eyesore and a nuisance. It signifies decadence and backwardness. A look at the Nigerian homes, toilets, streets, kitchens, corridors, gutters, staircases, markets, abattoirs, would reveal the very low levels of sanitation.

Poor environmental sanitation such as indiscriminate waste disposal is evidence of the crucial role environment occupies in deciding the health of a man. In fact, never before, in the history of Nigeria has the need become more imperative and urgent to sharpen our consciousness concerning our surroundings. For in such consciousness lies our dignity and salvation as a people and as a nation. This is because some Nigerian still go about with the dangerous impression that “dorti no dey kill black man” (Filth does not kill black man)

Organisation for Economic Co-Operation and Development (2013) reveals that air pollution kills more Africans than other major risk factor in 2013 as statistics for premature-deaths from Air pollution scores 712,479 in 2013. Also, World Health Organization report on air pollution in 2016 named four Nigerian cities among 20 of the world’s worst-ranked cities for air quality (WHO, 2016) cited in (Kazeem, 2017).

However, over the years, specific measures undertaken by the Nigerian government both in the past and present have not yielded significant success. Despite the fact that the objectives of environmental sanitation are to create and maintain conditions in the environment that will promote health and prevent diseases (Lucas and Gilles, 1973). Cited in Okon Emmanuel (2007). This is because Environmental Sanitation deals with: Methods for the disposal of excreta, sewage and community wastes to ensure that they are adequate and safe. Today, living in a sustainable environment has become an issue on international concern which is making headlines both in the print and electronic media. Also, global warming, climate change, green-house gases effect, depletion of ozone layer, acidic rain and other climatic and environmental issues are now the hot and prioritized topics in the global mass media and many local stations. Both the governments and the people depend on communication and updates from the mass media not only for disseminating information but also in setting agenda for the development and other allied activities. Hence, communication media become powerful tools for disseminating information on the environment. It is against this background that the research assesses the role of radio as a tool for public enlightenment towards achieving a clean environment in Ilorin metropolis.

1.1. Statement of the Problem

Although, media role on environmental sanitation is well researched but at present, little or no research has been conducted specifically on environmental sanitation in Ilorin. Equally, at the moment, many Nigerians never see cleaning their environment as a big deal while there is poor policies implementation on environmental sanitation in Nigeria as there is no or popular law on refuse disposal in Nigeria and the consequence penalty of the violators.

It is against this background that the research investigates the role of radio as a tool for public enlightenment towards achieving clean environment in Ilorin metropolis with the view to know how media come in, by educate, sensitize and enlightened on what need to be done and what has been done before.

1.2. Objectives of the Study

- To examine the extent at which radio stations have been able to sensitize the public on environmental sanitation.
- To examine the frequency of exposure of the people in Ilorin metropolis to environmental sanitation programme on radio.
- To determine the extent at which radio campaign(s) on cleaning environment have been able to change the attitude of the people positively towards environmental sanitation.
- To ascertain whether radio stations allot enough air time in discussing and reporting environmental sanitation activities and programmes.
- To find out way(s) by which radio can improve environmental sanitation culture among people in the Ilorin metropolis.

1.3. Research Questions

- To what extent has radio been able to sensitize the public on environmental sanitation?
 - What is the frequency of exposure of the people in Ilorin metropolis to environmental sanitation programme on radio.
 - To what extent does radio campaign(s) change the attitude of the people positively towards cleaning the environment?
 - Do radio stations in Ilorin allot enough air time in discussing and reporting environmental sanitation activities and programmes?
 - In what way(s) can radio improve environmental sanitation culture among people in Ilorin metropolis?
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2. Literature review

2.1. Radio Broadcasting

Radio is an electronic device that uses electromagnetic wave for the transmission of messages, information, communication and it possesses some attributes which place it upon the television broadcasting (Oyekanmi, 2006). Radio can give people a voice and offer a forum for dialogue between communities and government. Radio takes up this responsibility and ensures vulnerable groups in society are included and represented in their programme. Community radio stations educate, sensitize and inform these local audiences about issues that affect their lives: health, education, water, human rights, etc. This way, radio is a genuine tool for local development (Olutope, 2010).

2.2. Characteristics of Radio Broadcasting

Radio as a medium comes with its unique characteristics that makes it still very relevant despite the globalization, media convergence or intimidations by the new media. Below are some of the features of radio as put by (Alao and Olayinka, 2016).

- **Portability:** A radio receiver is portable, you can move around with your radio set from room to kitchen, to farm and almost anywhere including your toilet.
- **Simplicity:** Audio is very simple to operate unlike digital television and computer that require some training.
- **Imaginative:** Despite the fact that it is an audio based medium, yet you could visualize or 'see' in your mind what was being described while listening to radio programme. During election, some people visualize election campaign, voting process, announcement of winner, again don't you ever visualize advert on radio?
- **Less expensive:** As it is simple, it is also a cheaper medium in terms of production and even in terms of the receiving set. The cost of producing radio programme cannot be compared to that of television. Also, a small radio set can be bought for as low price as 500 naira. In fact, most of the GSM and Smartphone come with inbuilt radio.
- **Power or Electricity:** Radio does not rely on electric power supply before it can be powered. You can listen to radio using dry battery cells even if you do not have electricity or a generator. Thus, in a country like Nigeria and particularly in the village where there is either epileptic power supply or none at all radio is what majority turn to as a source of information.
- **Medium of everybody:** One does not have to be literate to listen to radio because most of the radio languages are natives since radio meant to serve indigenous taste wherever is located. Unless you are literate, you can't read a newspaper or read captions or text on television.
- **Fast medium:** Radio is considered to be a very fast medium in terms of information distribution because it requires less processing unlike television. It is a breaking news platform as it tells the story before other medium.
- **Reach wide audience:** Radio signal can be receive in remote places making it happening the potential to reach larger audience simultaneously.

2.3. Concept of Environmental Sanitation

Anijah-Obi, Eneji, Ubom, Dunnamah and William (2013) write that environmental sanitation is a term means low level of sanitation and gross environmental indiscipline in our cities and communities. Apart from the health significance of heaps of refuse as a health hazard, they also make our environment ugly, adding that environmental sanitation general cleaning of the surrounding to make it clean and tidy which capable of improving living. The problem of solid waste disposal in Nigeria has become a national malaise. Most of the poor sanitation takes place in Nigerian homes, toilets,

streets, kitchens, corridors, gutters, staircases, markets, abattoirs. The woe of poor environmental sanitation such as indiscriminate waste disposal is evidence of the crucial role environment occupies in deciding the health of a man.

In fact, never before, in the history of Nigeria has the need become more imperative and urgent to sharpen our consciousness concerning our surroundings. For in such consciousness lies our dignity and salvation as a people and as a nation. This is because some Nigerians still go about with the dangerous impression that “Filth does not kill black man”. However, over the years, specific measures undertaken by the Nigerian Government both in the past and present have not yielded significant success.

2.4. Objectives of Environmental Sanitation

The objectives of environmental sanitation are to create and maintain conditions in the environment that will promote health and prevent diseases (Lucas and Gilles, 2003). This is because environmental sanitation deals with:

- Methods for the disposal of excreta, sewage and community wastes to ensure that they are adequate and safe.
- Water supplies, to ensure that they are pure and wholesome.
- Housing to ensure that it is a character likely to:
 - Provide as few opportunities as possible for the direct transmission of disease especially respiratory and other highly infectious diseases.
 - Encourage healthful habits in the occupants.
 - Milk and other food supplies to ensure that they are safe.
 - Personal and public health cleanliness especially in relation to diseases.
 - Control of arthropod, rodent, mollusc or other alternative hosts associated with human disease.
 - Atmospheric conditions to ensure that the external atmosphere is free from deleterious elements and that internal conditions of workshops, houses etc are suitable for the occupations undertaken in them and finally,
 - Factories, workshops, dwellings, streets and the general environment, to ensure freedom from risk to health, whether mechanical or biological and to provide the best working and living conditions

2.5. Environmental Sanitation in Kwara State

Kwara State has become one of the states boasting of good environmental sanitation habits since the inauguration and launching of Month end Clean Sanitation under the ministry of environment and sanitation in which every Thursday of the week are meant for “shops environmental cleaning” every Saturday that last every month is the “general cleaning” which environmental vehicle patrolling around every day to collect the debris/waste and dump at “Kwara State Waste Management Camp”.

2.6. Role and Responsibility of Broadcast Media in Environmental Sanitation

These days, the world is not safe as disaster can strike at any moment. Reducing the losses of life and property caused by any disaster is a compelling objective now receiving worldwide attention. It is now being increasingly believed that the knowledge and technology base potentially applicable to the mitigation of disasters has grown so dramatically that it would be possible, through a concerted cooperative international effort, to save many lives and reduce human suffering, dislocation, disaster shock and economic losses simply by providing better information, communication and awareness (Prabhanjan and Rapaka, 2011).

However, media should show its preparedness, emergency management and critical infrastructure protection long before a disaster actually strikes. Now media-print, audio, video and web have accustomed to the modern behavior and needs. The journalists should have a total commitment and involvement and work for the betterment of the society (Prabhanjan and Rapaka, 2011). Broadcast media professionals should consider this situation in all importance and social accountability in the larger interest of preserving not only the age old traditions, culture and values of the land, but also protect the environment and ecology in the changing scenario of climate and strive for the sustainable development (Prabhanjan and Rapaka, 2011).

Responsible journalism requires providing socially useful contributions that deepen understanding of problems and encourage search for workable solutions. Media is to benefit the public. Social responsibility is the only criterion to distinguish journalism from blogging, disinformation or agenda-driven information. Of all the difficult problems facing humankind, climate change and poor environmental sanitation as widest impact of everyone especially in developing nations of the world (Sangeeta, 2010).

Broadcast media have an important role and a vital responsibility in providing accurate information to the public. In addition to official emergency broadcasts, media relay accounts for: What Happened? Where it happened? When it happened? Who or what was affected? Who are the more vulnerable? What is being done? Where it is safe to go? Areas to avoid (unsafe, or being worked on), When it is safe to go back? Where people can get help? Where to get more information on administration help or official help? Where is the rehabilitation centers located? The main principle of information provision, therefore, should be an ethical one: and so, during an emergency, media should be sensitive to the needs of the public in affected areas and should avoid misinformation and broadcast unconfirmed reports that may lead to despair and panic (Prabhanjan and Rapaka, 2011).

Most of the time media in Kwara State do inform people about dangers in duping waste on the flood drainage and importance of drainage evacuation. While agencies in charge of environmental sanitation are invested and interviewed on issues relating to the environment so as to ensure sustainable environment. Therefore, correct and reliable information disseminated through the media is an important instrument for balancing the possible effects of incorrect, misleading or even willfully distorted information.

2.7. Empirical Review

Radio programming and environmental health Communication: an assessment of the effectiveness of the Queen FM 94.1 programme "Oga Landlord". The research was carried out to assess the effectiveness of radio programme in communicating environmental sanitation in Zaria, Kaduna State using both qualitative and quantitative research approaches. Data was specifically gathered through interview, observation, questionnaire and focus group discussion in order to ascertain the effectiveness of the Queen FM 94.1 programme "Oga Landlord" in the light of dealing with environmental sanitation issues. The study finds out that radio was a powerful medium for health promotion, educating people on social issues and disseminating information to a wide variety of audiences. Furthermore, it was discovered that adequate and effective environmental sanitation practices are the foundation for health development whereas inadequate and improper sanitation and poor solid waste management remain two of the main transmitters of diseases in the world's developing countries. More so, it was revealed that depth and proper treatment is not given to environmental health issues in the presentation of "Oga Landlord". Also, audience participation and feedback mechanisms in the programme are through text messages and phone calls. The study thus recommended that other channels of social media should be inculcated into the programme to enhance audience participation. In order to sustain effective radio communication, broadcasters should be prepared to carry out formative researches on the audience. Therefore, it is imperative to propose that effective radio programming should be tailored towards having the desired impact on the audience which could result in behavioural change.

Broadcast Media in Promoting Environmental Awareness: A Study of Yobe State Broadcasting Cooperation Damaturu (YBC), Nigeria is another study that is related to the study at hand was conducted by the duo of Zannah and Kyari (2018) titled "Broadcast Media in Promoting Environmental Awareness: A Study of Yobe State Broadcasting Cooperation Damaturu (YBC), Nigeria" The core objective of their research was to examining the role of broadcast media in promoting environmental awareness in Yobe state, Nigeria. Zannah and Kyari (2018) employed two research instruments to obtain data i.e interviews and questionnaire. Purposive sampling methods were adopted for the study. These techniques enable the researchers to select the target respondents from a large group. The collected data is coded, edited and analyzed with the help of Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) software. Findings show that majority of respondents contacted in the survey are environmentally friendly by keep their houses and surroundings clean. Majority of them were satisfied with the presentation and content of environmental programmes aired by Yobe state broadcasting cooperation (YBC).

A good population of the respondents know about on which date World Environment Day is celebrated. The good thing that can be studied is that majority of the respondents remember the environmental awareness message of YBC and most of them wish to do something towards protecting and promoting their environment after listen to the programmes. (The radio campaign was aimed at creating awareness on promoting environmental issues by involving the people of the state to participate actively. A majority of the respondents admitted that information provided by the media is the main source for awareness on environmental problems. The study recommended that the environmental programmes by Yobe state broadcasting cooperation need to involve the voices of the people, volunteers and producers at grassroots level who have direct attachments with environmental issues. This has many advantages, since it provides a good chance for the community to air its environmental concern, it gives an opportunity for talented people to exercise the profession of journalism; and it is one means of running environmental media programs with a minimum cost.

Sanitation Exercise in Lagos State, Nigeria: The Imperative of Integrated Communication Strategy conducted by Nwakerendu (2016) is another study that is relevant to this study at hand with the objective of assessing the residents'

level of compliance with Lagos state environment sanitation particularly with the program directives. Focus group and interview data were generated to facilitate the investigation. Findings of the study revealed that compliance level was low in spite of the government's use of force to drive it. Equally, a combination of communication methods would be necessary for effective mobilization. The study recommended that an integrated mobilization communication strategy need to be adopted. Adding that the essence of this strategy is to enlighten, inform and mobilize Lagos state residents. It is also integrated because it would take into consideration the cosmopolitan nature of Lagos State. This strategy should be led by the relevant government agency, in collaboration with selected broadcast stations (radio and television), relevant private organizations, including telecommunication, ICT firms and advertising agencies, civil society organizations as well as ethnic nationalities.

2.8. Theoretical Framework: Development Media Theory

This is another theory on which this study is anchored, this theory was propounded by Dennis McQuail in 1987 cited in Anaeto, Onabanjo and Osifeso (2008). The theory canvasses media support for an existing government and its efforts to bring about socio-economic development. This theory was one of the two theories added to normative theories to make it six normative theories, other theory was Democratic Participant Theory.

It argues that until a nation is well established and its economic development well underway, media must be supportive rather than critical of government, but assist them in implementing their policies. Also, some scholars believed that development media theory was bone out from the Agenda Setting Theory espoused by McCombs and Shaw in 1972 which stated that the media tells us not what to think but what to think about. In other words, the amount of attention given to an issue in the press affects the level of importance assigned to that issue by the audience.

As the name implies, (Development Media Theory) the theory relates to media in third world nations or developing country. It favours journalism that seeks out good news, requires that bad news stories are treated with caution, for such stories could be economically damaging to a nation which is delicate for growth and change.

Just as the assumption of this theory is to focus on developing story and maintain caution when it comes to bad stories, therefore, media in developing nations should do everything within its power to ensure development such as reporting, discussing and stage campaigns on environmental sanitation and general sustainable development matter in order to promote hygienic life style.

3. Methodology

The objective of this chapter is to establish the broad methodological engagement of this study which is relevant for describing the strategies involved in research. Therefore, this chapter clearly states research design, research method, population of study, sample size, sample technique/procedure, instrument for data collection, validity and reliability of the instrument, method and instrument for data analysis and presentation. According to Kenpro (2012), research design is the overall strategy used in integrating the different component of the study in a coherent and logical way, so as to ensure the effective addressing of the research problem. Similarly, Malik (2011) cited in Cooper (n.d) wrote that research design constitute the template for collection, measurement and analysis of data. It is also a strategic framework for action that serves as a bridge between research questions and the execution, or implementation of the research strategy (Mafuwane, 2012).

This study which assessing the role of radio as a tool for public enlightenment towards achieving clean environment in Ilorin metropolis adopted survey research method. Abdulwahab (2012) writes that survey is a type of research method associated with research situation where the research subjects run into hundreds or even thousands, spreading across a large area. Pritha (2021) explained that a population is the entire group that you want to draw conclusions about. Showkat (nd) describe a population refers to any collection of specified group of human beings or of non-human entities such as objects, educational institutions, time units, geographical areas, prices of wheat or salaries drawn by individuals.

Okoye (2006) defines population of the study as the total number of elements within a given environment which a research is set to study. The population of this study comprises of residence of Ilorin who are 100,000. According to Macrotrends (2022), the current metro area population of Ilorin in 2022 is 1,000,000, a 2.67% increase from 2021. The study involves many strategic locations such as: Offa-Garage, Post office, Tanke, Asa-DAm, Gaa-Akanbi, Taiwo and Challenge etc. The population comprises of male and female, adult and young.

This is a way to select a part or portion from a sampling frame or population to represent the entire population. Omniconvert (2020) writes that the sample size is a term used in research for defining the number of subjects included

in a particular study. By sample size, we understand a group of subjects that are selected from the general population and is considered a representative of the real population for that specific study. Therefore, the sample size for this study was 400 through Taro Yamane formula.

4. Data analysis and interpretation

Analysis on the data obtained from the questionnaire administered to the respondents in Ilorin metropolis particularly at Offa-Garage, Post office, Tanke, Asa-Dam, Gaa-Akanbi, Taiwo and Challenge. As stated previously, four hundred (400) copies of questionnaires were earlier distributed, out of which, three hundred ninety-five (395) copies were returned while only three hundred and seventy (370) were completely filled. Hence, the data analysis is based on the 370 correctly filled questionnaires. However, frequency and percentage distribution method was used to present the data with the aid of tables

Table 1 Distribution of Respondents by Demography

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	179	48.4%
Female	191	51.6%
Total	370	100.0%
	Frequency	Percentage
Age Group		
Below 20 years	22	5.9%
20–25	31	8.4%
26–30	27	7.3%
31–35	72	19.5%
36–40	101	27.3%
41 and above	117	31.6%
Total	370	100.0%
	Frequency	Percentage
Marital Status		
Married	237	64.1%
Widow	11	2.9%
Single	122	33.0%
Total	370	100.0%
	Frequency	Percentage
Occupation		
Students	53	14.3%
Entrepreneur	62	16.8%
Civil Servant	88	23.8%
Artisan	106	28.6%
Farming	61	16.5%
Total	370	100.0%

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Analysis: From the table 1 above, 191 (51.6 %) respondents were female while 179 (48.4%) respondents were male. Thus, female respondents dominated the respondents. Also, 117 (31.6%) of respondents were 41 years and above, while 22 (5.9%) of respondents were below age years. Furthermore, 237 (64.1%) of the respondents were married whereas 122 (33%) were single. On occupation of the respondents, 106 (28.6%) of the respondents were artisans while 53 (14.3%) were students.

Table 2 Respondents' Listenership to Radio FM?

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	367	99.2%
No	3	0.8%
Total	370	100.0%
Source: Field Survey, 2024		

Analysis: From the table 2 above, 367 (99.2%) of the respondents claimed that they listen to F.M radio while only 3 (0.8%) of the respondents said they don't. Obviously, the majority of respondents (99.2%) were listening to F.M radio.

Table 3 Respondents' Listenership to the environmental sanitation programmes on the Radio?

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	263	71.1%
No	107	28.9%
Total	370	100.0%
Source: Field Survey, 2024		

Analysis: From the table 3 above, 263 (71.1%) of the respondents agreed that they listen to the environmental sanitation programmes on the radio whereas, 107 (28.9%) of the respondents claimed otherwise. Hence, it is clear that, majority of respondents (71.1%) listen to the environmental sanitation programmes on the radio.

Table 4 Frequency to the exposure of environmental sanitation programmes on the radio

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Very often	63	17%
Often	237	64%
Rarely	67	18.1%
Not at all	3	0.8%
Total	370	100.0%
Source: Field Survey, 2024		

Analysis: From the table 4 above, 237 (64%) of the respondents opined that they are often exposed to environmental sanitation programmes on the radio while just 3 (0.8%) of the respondents claimed that they never listen to environment sanitation programmes on radio. Thus, the majority of the respondents (64%) were often exposed to the environmental sanitation programmes on radio.

Table 5 Level of listenership and contributions to the programme generally?

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Very High	52	14%
High	60	16.2%
Average	244	66%
Low	14	3.8%
Total	370	100.0%

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Analysis: From the table 5 above, 244 (66%) of the respondents admitted that they listen and contribute to environmental sanitation programmes on average whereas, 14 (3.8%) of the respondents said they listen and contribute to the programme on environmental sanitation programmes on radio at a low extent. Therefore, substantial numbers of respondents (66%) averagely listen and contribute to the programme environmental sanitation programmes on radio.

Table 6 Radio sensitization of the respondents about cleaning the environment

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agreed	56	15%
Agreed	241	65%
Neutral	60	16.2%
Disagreed	13	3.5%
Strongly Disagreed	0	0%
Total	370	100.0%

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Analysis: From the table 6 above, 241 (65%) of the respondents agreed that sanitation programmes on radio sensitize them about cleaning the environment, whereas 13 (3.5%) of the respondents disagreed that sanitation programmes on radio sensitize them about cleaning the environment. This implies that the programme sensitized them about cleaning the environment.

Table 7 Influence of Radio on the respondents' behaviour towards cleaning environment?

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agreed	101	27.3%
Agreed	200	54%
Neutral	63	17%
Disagreed	10	2.7%
Strongly Disagreed	0	0%
Total	370	100.0%
Source: Field Survey, 2024		

Analysis: From the table 7 above, 200 (54%) of the respondents agreed that the sanitation campaign on radio influenced their behaviour towards cleaning the environment, while 10 (2.7%) of the respondents disagreed that the sanitation campaign on radio influenced their behaviour towards cleaning the environment. This shows that the sanitation campaigns on radio influenced respondents' behaviour towards cleaning the environment.

Table 8 Effectiveness of the Radio sanitation campaigns on the respondents

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Highly Effective	70	19%
Effective	190	51.4%
Fair	84	22.7%
Not Effective	26	7%
Total	370	100.0%

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Analysis: From the table above, 190 (51.4%) of the respondents agreed that sanitation campaigns on radio were effective, while 26 (7%) of the respondents claimed that sanitation campaigns on radio were not effective. This indicates that the campaigns on the Radio were effective.

Table 9 What type of message does radio pass to you on environmental sanitation?

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
When to carry out monthly sanitation	60	16.2%
Covering people performing environmental sanitation	204	51.1%
Interviewing sanitation enforcers	80	21.6%
Government policies on environmental sanitation	26	7.0%
Total	370	100.0%

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Analysis: From the table above, 204 (51.1) of the respondents revealed that they received messages covering people performing environmental sanitation while 26 (7%) of the respondents claimed that they received messages on government policies on environmental sanitation. Therefore, many of the respondents received messages covering people performing environmental sanitation.

Table 10 Radio stations should double their effort towards enlightening people about environmental sanitation?

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agreed	101	27.3%
Agreed	200	54%
Neutral	63	17%
Disagreed	10	2.7%
Strongly Disagreed	0	0%
Total	370	100.0%
Source: Field Survey, 2024		

Analysis: From table above, 200 (54%) of the respondents agreed that radio stations should double their effort towards enlightening people about environmental sanitation, while 10 (2.7%) of the respondents still disagreed, claiming that radio stations are doing well in enlightening people about environmental sanitation. However, radio stations are charged to double their effort towards in enlightening people about environmental sanitation.

Table 11 Dedicated radio programme on environmental sanitation in Kwara State?

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	261	70.5%
No	109	29.5%
Total	370	100.0%

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Analysis: From the table above, 261 (70%) of the respondents agreed that there are dedicated programmes on environmental sanitation in radio stations in Kwara State whereas, 109 (29.5%) of the respondents denied. This shows that there are dedicated radio programmes on environmental sanitation in Kwara State.

Table 12 On what radio station in Kwara State is environmental sanitation often aired?

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Radio Kwara	132	35.7%
Harmony FM	68	17.4%
Sobi FM	63	17.0%
Royal FM	40	10.8%
Albraka FM	29	7.8%
Midland FM	15	4.0%
Raypower FM	23	6.2%
Total	370	100.0%

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Analysis: From the table above, 132 (35.7%) of the respondents often get their environmental sanitation messages from Radio Kwara, while 15 (4%) of the respondents get theirs from Midland FM. Therefore, the majority of respondents (35.7%) admitted that they get their environmental sanitation messages from Radio Kwara.

Table 13 Respondents' responses on whether radio campaign(s) programmes change their attitude positively towards cleaning the environment

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agreed	77	20.8%
Agreed	221	59.7%
Neutral	42	11.0%
Disagreed	13	3.5%
Strongly Disagreed	17	4.6%
Total	370	100.0%

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Analysis: From the table 13 above, 221 (59.7%) of the respondents disclosed that radio campaign(s) programmes have changed their attitude positively towards cleaning the environment, whereas 13 (4.6%) of the respondents disagreed. Nonetheless, the largest percentage of the respondents (59.7%) unveiled that radio campaign(s) programmes have changed their attitude positively towards cleaning the environment.

Table 14 Respondents’ responses on whether radio stations in Ilorin allot enough air time in discussing and reporting environmental sanitation activities and programmes

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agreed	47	12.7%
Agreed	33	8.9%
Neutral	41	11.0%
Disagreed	222	60.0%
Strongly Disagreed	27	7.3%
Total	370	100.0%

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Analysis: From table 14 above, 222 (60%) of the respondents disagreed that radio stations in Ilorin allot enough air time in discussing and reporting environmental sanitation activities and programmes, equally, 27 (7.3%) of the respondents disagreed. This shows radio stations in Ilorin didn't allot enough air time to discussing and reporting environmental sanitation activities and programmes.

Table 15 In what way(s) can radio improve environmental sanitation culture among people in Ilorin metropolis?

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Through news on the importance of hygiene	66	17.8%
Through programmes on environmental sanitation	104	28.0%
Through live coverage of environmental sanitation	200	54.0%
Total	370	100.0%

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Analysis: From the table above, 200 (54) of the respondents observed that radio stations in Kwara State can improve environmental sanitation culture among people in Ilorin metropolis through the live coverage of environmental sanitation while 66 (17.8%) of the respondents can improve environmental sanitation culture among people in Ilorin metropolis through news on the important of hygiene. Consequently, the majority of respondents (54%) suggested that live coverage of environmental sanitation can improve environmental sanitation culture among people in the Ilorin metropolis.

Table 16 Respondents’ responses on whether radio change their attitude positively towards environmental sanitation

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	271	73.2%
No	99	26.7%
Total	370	100.0%

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Analysis: From the table above, 271 (73.2%) of the respondents admitted that radio programme changed their attitude positively towards environmental sanitation whereas, 99 (26.7%) of the respondents responded against that. That shows that radio programmes changed their attitude positively towards environmental sanitation.

Table 17 Extent at which radio educated the respondents on the danger of poor sanitation

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agreed	67	18.1%
Agreed	214	57%
Neutral	41	11.0%
Disagreed	27	7.2%
Strongly Disagreed	21	5.6%
Total	370	100.0%
Source: Field Survey, 2024		

Analysis: From the table 17 above, 214 (57%) of the respondents agreed that radio educates them on the danger of poor sanitation whereas, 21 (5.6%) of the respondents strongly disagreed. Hence, the radio stations in kwara state have really educated them on the danger of poor sanitation.

Table 18 Why do you think environmental sanitation should be encouraged?

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
To prevent Ebola/Coronavirus, etc.	67	18.0%
To prevent outbreak of cholera	206	55.7%
To make society tidy/hygienic	97	26.2%
Total	370	100.0%

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Analysis: From the table above, 206 (55.7%) of the respondents think that environmental sanitation should be encouraged to prevent outbreak of cholera while 67 (18%) of the respondents want that environmental sanitation should be encouraged to prevent ebola/coronavirus etc. Thus, the majority of respondents (55.7%) suggested that environmental sanitation should be encouraged to prevent outbreak of cholera.

Table 19 How would you rate the level of sanitation in Ilorin?

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Very High	54	14.6%
High	198	53.5%
Average	57	15.4%
Low	42	11.4%
Very Low	19	5.1%
Total	370	100.0%

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Analysis: From the table 19 above, 198 (53.5%) of the respondents were of the opinion that environmental sanitation is high in Ilorin whereas, 19 (5.1%) of the respondents described environmental sanitation in Ilorin as very low. That shows that the level of environmental sanitation is high in Ilorin.

5. Discussion

Having analyzed the data collected from respondents in the Ilorin metropolis, the following are the major findings. On questions that border on demography, female respondents (51.6%) dominated the response rate. Also, the majority of respondents (31.6%) were aged 41 years and above. Furthermore, (64.1%) of the respondents were married. One occupation of the respondents (28.6%) were artisans.

5.1. Research Question 1: What is the frequency of exposure of the people in Ilorin metropolis to environmental sanitation programmes on radio.

Table 2 answered this research question, as the responses from the respondents indicate that the majority of respondents (99.2%) do listen to radio FM. It is clear that, the majority of respondents (71.1%) listen to the environmental sanitation programmes on the radio, equally, the majority of them (64%) claimed that they listen to the programmes on radio often. Similarly, substantial numbers of respondents (66%) averagely listen and contribute to the programme environmental sanitation programmes on radio.

5.2. Research Question 2: Do you listen to the environmental sanitation programmes on the Radio?

Also, the majority of respondents (65%) agreed that sanitation programmes on radio sensitize them about cleaning the environment. Similarly, the majority of respondents (54%) agreed that sanitation campaigns on radio influenced respondents' behaviour towards cleaning the environment. Many of respondents (54%) agreed that sanitation campaigns on radio were effective, and many of respondents (51.1%) admitted that they received messages covering people performing environmental sanitation.

However, the majority of respondents (54%) want radio stations to double their effort towards enlightening people about environmental sanitation. Meanwhile, many of the respondents (70.5%) pronounced that there are dedicated programmes on environmental sanitation in radio stations in Kwara State, majority of respondents (35.7%) admitted that they get their environmental sanitation messages from Radio Kwara.

Nonetheless, the largest percentage of the respondents (59.7%) unveiled that radio campaign(s) programmes have changed their attitude positively towards cleaning the environment. Largest percentage of the respondents (60%) disagreed that radio stations in Ilorin allot enough air time in discussing and reporting environmental sanitation activities and programmes.

Consequently, the majority of respondents (54%) suggested that live coverage of environmental sanitation can improve environmental sanitation culture among people in the Ilorin metropolis. It is obvious that many of the respondents (73.2%) claimed that radio has changed their attitude positively towards environmental sanitation. Hence, the majority of the respondents (57%) agreed that radio stations have really educated them on the danger of poor sanitation. Majority of respondents (55.7%) suggested that environmental sanitation should be encouraged to prevent the outbreak of cholera. Similarly, the majority of the respondents (53.5%) opined that environmental sanitation is high in Ilorin.

6. Conclusion

Having analyzed the data collected from respondents, it is safe to conclude that the majority of respondents (99.2%) were listening to F.M radio. It is clear that, the majority of respondents (71.1%) listen to the environmental sanitation programmes on the radio, equally, the majority of them (64%) claimed that they listen to environmental sanitation programmes on radio often. Similarly, substantial numbers of respondents (66%) averagely listen and contribute to the programme environmental sanitation programmes on radio.

Also, the majority of respondents (65%) agree that sanitation programmes on radio sensitize them about cleaning the environment. Similarly, the majority of respondents (54%) agree that sanitation campaigns on radio influenced respondents' behaviour towards cleaning the environment. Many of respondents (54%) agree that sanitation campaigns on radio were effective, and many of respondents (51.1%) admitted that they received messages covering people performing environmental sanitation.

However, the majority of respondents (54%) want radio stations to double their effort towards enlightening people about environmental sanitation. Meanwhile, many of the respondents (70.5%) pronounced that there are dedicated

programmes on environmental sanitation in radio stations in Kwara State, majority of respondents (35.7%) admitted that they get their environmental sanitation messages from Radio Kwara.

Nonetheless, the largest percentage of the respondents (59.7%) show that radio campaign(s) programmes have changed their attitude positively towards cleaning the environment. Largest percentage of the respondents (60%) disagree that radio stations in Ilorin allot enough air time in discussing and reporting environmental sanitation activities and programmes.

Consequently, the majority of respondents (54%) suggested that live coverage of environmental sanitation can improve environmental sanitation culture among people in the Ilorin metropolis. It is obvious that many of the respondents (73.2%) claimed that radio has changed their attitude positively towards environmental sanitation. Hence, the majority of the respondents (57%) agree that radio stations have really educated them on the danger of poor sanitation. Majority of respondents (55.7%) also suggested that environmental sanitation should be encouraged to prevent outbreak of cholera. And, the majority of the respondents (53.5%) opined that environmental sanitation is high in Ilorin.

Recommendations

After critical examination and review of the previous literatures, the theories, and data gathered from the field, the following are therefore recommended in line with the key findings of the research:

It is recommended that broadcast media should equip their journalists with sophisticated equipment or toolkit to cover scientific issues such as: covering areas with less effort on the environmental sanitation or poor environmental sanitation, flooding disaster, heavy wind and storm without much stress.

Broadcast media outfits should organize special seminars and workshops for their reporters on how best to cover scientific and environmental news to better show professionalism so that people can be better informed.

Special desk suggested to be called environmental and climate desk should be created and equipped with scientific and investigative journalists to maintain the desk for effective and efficient dissemination of information on sanitation, weather, climate and other environmental matters.

Media houses should design programmes for people to be more educated and alerted on environmental hazards, challenges and sanitation.

Other radio stations should be encouraged to pay utmost focus in reporting environmental sanitation programmes and campaigns by allocating more air time for environmental sanitation. This will improve the level of environmental sanity. As such, Radio Kwara as a media platform should ensure the principle of fairness, balance and objectivity is adhered to.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

There is no conflict of interest

Statement of ethical approval

Ethical approval was obtained prior to data collection. All participants were informed that their participation was voluntary, and that the study was conducted solely for academic research purposes. Participants were assured of the confidentiality and anonymity of their responses.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study, following a clear explanation of the study's aims, procedures, and their rights as participants.

Sources of Funding

This study received no specific grants from public, commercial, or non-profit funding agencies.

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